

In the case of succinyl and phthalyl chlorides, it has been possible to isolate the corresponding imides (II) and (X), which on treatment with dilute alkali in the cold give N^1 -succinyl- N^4 -acetylsulphanilamide (III) and N^1 -phthalyl- N^4 -acetylsulphanilamide (XI) respectively.

It is interesting to note that the action of (j) on the potassium salt of *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonamide gives N^1 -pyridine-2 : 3-dicarbo- N^4 -acetyldisulphanilamide (XIV).

While N^1 -glutaryl (V), N^1 -adipyl (VII) and N^1 -phthalyl-sulphanilamide (XI) can be obtained by hydrolysis of the corresponding N^1 -acyl- N^4 -acetylsulphanilamides (IV), (VI), and (XI) respectively, hydrolysis of N^1 -succinyl-, N^1 -azelayl-, N^1 -sebacyl-, N^1 -2-carboxy-furan-5-carbo- N^4 -acetylsulphanilamides and N^1 -pyridino-2 : 3-dicarbo- N^4 -acetyldisulphanilamide (III, VIII, IX, XIII and XIV) respectively leads to their cleavage.

Azelaic and sebacic acid chlorides have also been condensed with sulphanilamide to get the corresponding N^4 -azelayldisulphanilamide (XV) and N^4 -sebacyl-disulphanilamide (XVI), which have not been reported so far.

Curiously enough, the keto and pyrone oxygens and not the carboxy groups of chelidonic acid react with sulphanilamide giving *N-p*-sulphonamidophenyl-4-(*p*-aminobenzene sulphonimino)-chelidamic acid (XVII). This is due to the basic nature of the keto oxygen and the easy replaceability of pyrone oxygen by ammonia and amines as observed by Collie (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 971) and Bedekar *et al.* (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 468).

The structure of (XVII) has been established from (i) a study of its properties, (ii) from the estimation of N, S, and NH_2 group and (iii) from the determination of its equivalent weight. It dissolves with effervescence in bicarbonate solution indicating the presence of free carboxyl groups. Its solubility in dilute hydrochloric acid and diazotizability prove the presence of free NH_2 group. The product (XVII) contains 1.5 moles of water of crystallisation which, along with 2 molecules of carbon dioxide, are eliminated when it is heated at 100-120° for 2 hours, leading to the formation of *N-p*-sulphonamidophenyl-4-(*p*-aminobenzene sulphonimino)-1 : 4-dihydropyridine (XVIII).

Fusion of *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphochloride and diethyldihydrocollidine dicarboxylate gives *N*-(N^1 -sulphonyl)-dihydrocollidine dicarboxylic acid (XIX) by

N-p-Sulphonamidophenyl-4-(p-aminophenylsulphanimino)-1 : 4-dihydropyridine (XVIII).—The above compound (XVII, 1g.) was first heated at 100° for 10 minutes and then at 160° for 45 minutes. At about 110° the substance fused and frothed. After cooling, the product, insoluble in water, was purified by dissolving in alkali and precipitating with HCl, m.p. 210°, yield 0.6g.

N-(N¹-Sulphanityl)-dihydrocollidine Dicarboxylic Acid (XIX).—Diethyl dihydrocollidine dicarboxylate (4.2 g.) and *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonyl chloride (4.8 g) were heated together at 130-135° for 1 hour. Reaction started at 120° with evolution of HCl and later, ethyl acetate was formed. The product was isolated and crystallised from a large volume of alcohol, m. p. 300° (decomp), yield 6.4 g.

N-(N¹-Acetylsulphanityl)-chelidamic Acid (XX).—To chelidamic acid (2 g.), suspended in dry pyridine (15 c.c.), *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphonyl chloride (2.5 g.) was added with shaking and refluxed on a sand-bath for 2 hours. After cooling, the product was filtered out and washed with a little alcohol. It was crystallised from water, m.p. 227°, yield 3.2 g.

Equivalents.—The compounds were titrated to phenolphthalein end-point and required one equivalent of alkali for the sulphonamido group and one equivalent, for the acid group, wherever present.

TABLE I

No.	Formula	M.p.	% Nitrogen		Equivalent	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
I.	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	1590 (d)	8.72	8.53	325.5	328.0
II.	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	259	9.36	9.50	—	—
III.	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	195	9.14	8.92	155.3	157.0
IV.	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	255 (d)	8.67	8.54	166.0	164.0
V.	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	187	10.00	9.80	140.0	143.0
VI.	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	200 (d)	8.24	8.18	170.4	171.0
VII.	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	170	9.00	9.23	152.8	150.0
VIII.	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	245	7.14	7.26	192.7	192.0
IX.	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	250 (d)	7.21	7.00	196.4	199.0
X.	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	295	8.15	8.12	—	—
XI.	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	304	7.58	7.73	180.2	181.0
XII.	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S	385	8.62	8.75	158.2	160.0
XIII.	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S (a)	230 (d)	7.91	8.07	177.4	176.0
XIV.	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂ (b)	308	12.37	11.52	—	—
XV.	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	231 (d)	11.60	11.31	—	—
XVI.	C ₂ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	239 (d)	10.68	10.98	—	—
XVII.	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂ · ½ H ₂ O (c)	165	10.70	10.80	252.4	259.5
XVIII.	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂ (e)	210	13.02	13.86	—	—
XIX.	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S (f)	300 (d)	7.82	7.65	152.5	153.6
XX.	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S (g)	227	7.20	7.37	180.0	180.0
XXI.	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S (h)	255 (d)	8.25	8.30	—	—

(a) S found : 9.40 ; requires 9.10%

(b) S 11.20 11.45

(c) S 12.01 12.33 ; NH₂ found : 0.983 ; requires 1.0

(e) S 15.50 15.84 ; " " 0.999 1.0

(f) S 8.50 8.75 ; " " 0.940 1.0

(g) S 8.20 8.42 ; " " " "

(h) S 9.20 9.47 ; " " 0.921 1.0

(d) denotes decomposed.